

FEEL THE FREEDOM IN THE WORKS OF WALT WHITMAN

Fayzullayeva Nigina Sur'at qizi

Asia International University, English chair

fayzullayevaniginasuratqizi@oxu.uz

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Abstract. *Walt Whitman was one of America's most celebrated poets, indeed captures a sense of freedom in his works through his exploration of individuality, democracy, and the vastness of the American landscape.*

Key words: *individuality, democracy, and the vastness of the American landscape.*

ПОЧУВСТВУЙТЕ СВОБОДУ В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ УОЛТА УИТМЕНА

Аннотация. *Уолт Уитмен был одним из самых знаменитых поэтов Америки. Он действительно передает чувство свободы в своих произведениях, исследуя индивидуальность, демократию и необъятность американского ландшафта.*

Ключевые слова: *индивидуальность, демократия и необъятность американского ландшафта.*

Walt Whitman, one of America's most celebrated poets, indeed captures a sense of freedom in his works through his exploration of individuality, democracy, and the vastness of the American landscape.

In his seminal work "Leaves of Grass," Whitman celebrates the diversity of human experience and the vastness of the American continent. His poetry often reflects the idea of freedom not only in its literal sense but also in its spiritual and existential dimensions. Whitman's free verse style itself is emblematic of this sense of liberation, breaking away from traditional forms and structures.

In poems like "Song of Myself," Whitman revels in the idea of the self as expansive and inclusive, embracing all aspects of human existence without judgment. He celebrates the individual as well as the collective, blurring boundaries between self and others, suggesting a deep sense of interconnectedness and freedom from societal constraints.

Moreover, Whitman's portrayal of the American landscape, from the bustling cities to the untamed wilderness, reflects a sense of boundless opportunity and possibility. His imagery often evokes a feeling of vastness and openness, inviting readers to contemplate the infinite possibilities of existence.

Walt Whitman, often hailed as the father of American poetry, remains a towering figure in literature, renowned for his ability to capture the essence of freedom in his works. Through his groundbreaking poetry collection "Leaves of Grass" and other notable pieces, Whitman encapsulates the spirit of liberation in various forms, resonating with readers across generations.

At the core of Whitman's exploration of freedom lies his celebration of individuality. In "Song of Myself," arguably his most famous poem, Whitman exalts the self in all its complexity, declaring, "I celebrate myself, / And what I assume you shall assume, / For every atom belonging to me as good belongs to you." Here, he embraces the idea of the individual as inherently valuable, deserving of recognition and respect. Through his free verse style, Whitman rejects the constraints

of traditional poetic forms, allowing his words to flow unrestrained, mirroring the unrestricted nature of the human spirit.

Whitman's conception of freedom extends beyond the individual to encompass the collective experience of humanity. In "I Hear America Singing," he portrays the diverse voices of the American people, each contributing to the symphony of the nation. From the laborer to the carpenter to the mother, Whitman celebrates the myriad expressions of life, emphasizing the democratic ideal of equality and inclusivity. Through his poetry, he envisions a society where every voice is heard and every person is valued—a vision deeply rooted in the principles of freedom and democracy.

Furthermore, Whitman's portrayal of the American landscape evokes a sense of boundless possibility and exploration. In poems like "Crossing Brooklyn Ferry" and "To a Locomotive in Winter," he celebrates the power of progress and the expansive nature of the land. Through vivid imagery and immersive language, Whitman invites readers to embark on a journey of discovery, traversing the vast expanse of the country and the human experience alike.

Ultimately, Whitman's works serve as a testament to the enduring quest for freedom in all its forms. Whether exploring the depths of the individual psyche or the breadth of the American landscape, he inspires readers to embrace the inherent freedom of existence, to celebrate the richness of life, and to strive for a world where liberty and justice flourish.

In today's world, Whitman's message remains as relevant as ever, reminding us to cherish our freedoms, both personal and collective, and to honor the inherent dignity of every individual. Through his poetry, we are invited to feel the palpable sense of liberation that permeates his words—a freedom that transcends boundaries, unites humanity, and endures through the ages.

Overall, Whitman's works resonate with a profound sense of freedom that transcends mere political or social definitions. Through his poetry, he invites readers to embrace the fullness of life, to revel in their individuality, and to explore the expansive landscapes of both the external world and the human spirit.

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